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**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Research Article****A CROSS-SECTIONAL SURVEY TO CREATE THE
WAKEFULNESS ON THE SUBJECT OF SPECIAL EFFECTS
OF SMOKING AMONG PEOPLE OF LAHORE CITY**¹Dr. Tanzeela Iram, ²Dr Qurrat ul Ain, ³Ghanwa Abbas¹WMO, Combined Military Hospital, Rawalpindi²Woman Medical Officer, Punjab Health Department, Rawalpindi,³Allama Iqbal Memorial Teaching Hospital Sialkot**Article Received:** February 2019**Accepted:** March 2019**Published:** April 2019**Abstract:**

Introduction: Passive smoking is an outcome of exhaled smoke by other smokers (cigar or cigarette) in the air which is inhaled by others. Breathing in such an environment is an act of passive smoking. This act of taking smoke inside is also significantly hazardous and risky for non-smokers. The safe level of passive smoking is still unknown.

Objective: This research was carried out with an objective to create awareness among people about the possible side effects and risks of passive smoking.

Methods: We carried out this cross-sectional survey to gather information about the awareness of people about passive smoking through a self-administered questionnaire. The questionnaire consisted of demographic information, cigarettes smoked, family history and smoking habit.

Results: Outcomes reflect that twenty percent of people were not aware of passive smoking; whereas, eighty percent of the population was aware of the side effects of passive smoking. Most of the people who were about passive smoking were in the age bracket of 20 – 30 years.

Conclusion: In comparison to other age brackets, most of the people who were about passive smoking were in the age bracket of 20 – 30 years.

Keywords: Side Effects, Cigar, Awareness, Passive smoking and Hazards.

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INTRODUCTION:

The International Agency for Research on Cancer of the World Health Organization concluded in 2004 that there was sufficient evidence that second-hand smoke caused cancer in humans (IARC 2004). Those who work in environments where smoke is not regulated are at higher risk. Workers particularly at risk of exposure include those in installation repair and maintenance, construction and extraction, and transportation. It is estimated that living or working in a place where smoking is permitted increases the nonsmokers' risk of developing heart disease by 25–30% and lung cancer by 20–30%. The risk of asthma, Risk of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) increases in passive smoking. Exposure to secondhand smoke may increase the risk of cognitive impairment and dementia in adults 50 and over. Recent studies comparing women exposed to Environmental Tobacco Smoke and non-exposed women, demonstrate that women exposed while pregnant have higher risks of delivering a child with congenital abnormalities, longer lengths, smaller head circumferences, and low birth weight. Overall increased risk of death in both adults, where it is estimated to kill 53,000 nonsmokers per year, making it the 3rd leading cause of preventable death in the U.S and in children.

The World Health Organization states that passive smoking causes about 600,000 deaths a year, and about 1% of the global burden of disease. According to US Surgeon General 2006 report, people are exposed to secondhand smoke at home, in the workplace, and in other public places such as bars, restaurants, and recreation venues. It is harmful and hazardous to the health of the general public and particularly dangerous to children. It increases the risk of serious respiratory problems in children, such as a greater number and severity of asthma attacks and lower respiratory tract infections, and increases the risk for middle ear infections. It is also a known human carcinogen; cancer-causing agent. Inhaling secondhand smoke causes lung cancer and coronary heart disease in nonsmoking adults. Tobacco smoke contains over 4000 chemicals that are potentially toxic to humans. Carbon monoxide decreases hemoglobin transport and saturation. Nicotine decreases prostacyclin synthesis and aggregation of thrombocytes in blood vessels, which leads to the narrowing of the arteries of the foetus, as well as neonates and infants. Tager 2008, further explains that nicotine crosses the placenta freely and, in animal models that include primates, has profound effects on fetal lung development that range through altered glucose metabolism, inhibition of fibroblast proliferation, damage to type I epithelial cells, increased proliferation of type II cells, disruption of

the elastin network and alterations in cell signalling with resultant decreases in apoptosis in the developing lung. All of these result in decreased numbers and enlargement of alveoli, emphysema-like changes and alterations in lung function. The rationale of doing this research is to make people aware of the lethal effects caused by second hand smoking or passive smoking. In passive smoking the person sitting next to the smoker is equally affected so he is also on the edge of developing cancers, cardiovascular defects and respiratory problems. So for the sake of community it is important to make people aware that breathing in the atmosphere full of smoke can cause them health problems similar to that of a smoker. For making this world smoke free health education is most important.

A Report of the Surgeon General-2001 indicates that exposure to environmental tobacco smokes is a cause of lung cancer and coronary heart disease among women who are lifetime nonsmokers. Studies have also linked exposure to secondhand smoke during early children to increased risk of sudden infant death syndrome, asthmas, and other respiratory illnesses, ear infections, and a host of developmental, cognitive and behavioral problems. Infants born to women exposed to environmental tobacco smoke during pregnancy have a small decrement in birth weight and a slightly increased risk of intrauterine growth retardation compared to infants of non-exposed women. Researchers in Malmo found that 80 per cent of the women whose babies were below average in weight were routinely exposed to secondhand smoke during pregnancy. In 1999, researchers warned that heavy smoking by teenagers can cause genetic mutations in the lungs, forever predisposing them to lung cancer—even if they quit. Secondhand smoke may prove just as bad. In a study at the University of Louisville, associate professor Steven Myers and his team measured the levels of 4-ABP, a cancer-causing agent in tobacco smoke, in the blood of 475 pregnant women and their fetuses. As expected, 4-ABP levels were significantly elevated in mothers who smoked, compared with nonsmokers, and in their fetuses. The unpleasant surprise: Levels were also high in nonsmoking mothers exposed to secondhand smoke for eight or more hours a day at home or work.

METHOD:

Study Design: Descriptive cross-sectional study will be done

Study Universe: Lahore

Study Population: General population of Lahore city.

Study Setting: Lahore city

Duration of Study: December, 2018 to January, 2019

Sample Size: Estimated using WHO software S size and by using formula of estimating the population proportion with specified relative precision. At

confidence level of 95 % with anticipated population proportion of 70% and relative precision of 10% the minimum sample size was taken as 100.

RESULTS:

Table 1: Age of population selected for the research

Age	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
20 - 30 Years	60	60	60	56
30 - 40 Years	20	20	20	44
40 - 50 Years	20	20	20	100
Total	100	100	100	100

Results:

It states that:

- 60% people belongs to 20-30 years age group
- 20% people belongs to 30-40 years age group
- 20% people belongs to 40-50 years age group

Table 2: Gender percentage of representing population

Sex	Number	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Female	20	20	20	40
Male	80	80	80	100
Total	100	100	100	

Results:

It states that:

- 20% people were female
- 80% people were male

Table 3: Awareness in the community regarding Passive smoking

Passive Smoking Awareness	Number	Percentage	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
No	20	20	20	42
Yes	80	80	80	100
Total	100	100	100	

DISCUSSION:

The respondents divided into 3 different age groups. First age group consists of respondents between the ages of 20 to 30 years and second age group comprises of the respondents between the ages of 30 to 40 years. The third group has the respondents between the ages of 40 to 50 years old. The study also shows about the frequency of three different age groups. The first group between 20-30 years of age has the 60% of the total respondents and among them 50% are male and 10% are female respondents. The second group of 30-40 years of age has the 20% respondents and among them 15% are male and 5% are female. The third group of 40-50 years of age has 20% respondents in which 15% are male and 5% are

female. The respondents consist of both male and female participants. The respondents have 80% male frequency and 20% female frequency. The results regarding awareness shows that 80% of the people are aware about it whereas only 20% of the people are not aware about passive smoking. Also among the people who are aware, 70% are males and 10% are females and in non-aware people the percentage of male and female are 10% respectively.

The study was conducted regarding the awareness of effects of passive smoking among the general population of Lahore city. A group of 100 people were selected for the research that includes 80% male respondents and 20% female respondents. The

output of the research shows that the population between the age group of 20 to 30 years is 60 % and the population between 30 to 40 years is 20 %. The population between 40 to 50 years of age is 20 %. According to conclusion of research study, 80% people are aware and 20% people are not aware about the harmful effects of passive smoking. People of age group between 20-30 years have more awareness about harmful effects of passive smoking as compared to other age group. The Questionnaire has been formulated to know about the awareness about the passive smoking in which we address the occupation, living standard and exposure to smoking. The purpose of the survey is to know about how much the population of Lahore city is aware of the effects of passive smoking and how many of them take the preventive measures to protect themselves from passive smoking. The conclusion of the survey shows that majority of the community have the awareness about the passive smoking but they are ignorant about their health and reluctant to prevent themselves from passive smoking.

CONCLUSION:

Our study concluded that 80% people were aware of effects of passive smoking, 20% people were not aware of effects of passive smoking, People of age group between 20-30 years of age have more awareness of effect of passive smoking as compared to other age groups. Study conducted on awareness regarding the effects of passive smoking among general population of Lahore city. 100 people were selected for study and study was conducted at Lahore city by a team of 5 members and data was analyzed through SPSS-22 software.

REFERENCES:

1. Protection, Better Nutrition, 0405668X, Nov 2003, Database: Academic Search Premier, Vol. 65(11)
2. Smokers put others at risk, too, USA Today, MAY 26, 2004. Secondhand Smoke More Dangerous Than Thought, Tufts University health & Nutrition Letter, 15260143, Jun 2003, Database: Academic Search Premier, Vol. 21, (4).
3. Tracy Hampton, 11.3/2004, Vol. 292, (17), p2072 Chemical Linked to Bladder Cancer in Smokers May Play Wider Role, Journal of American Medical Association.
4. Tagger, I.B. 2008. The effects of second/hand and direct exposure to tobacco smoke on asthma and lung function in adolescence. Pediatric Respiratory Reviews. Consulted: 07.01.2011, vol.9, (29)-38.
5. Ana Navas-Acien 6/9/2004, Secondhand Tobacco Smoke in Public Places in Latin America, JAMA: Journal of the American Medical Association, Vol. 291(22), p2741
6. Bklyn Forum 11/28/2002, Addresses Secondhand Smoke, New York Amsterdam News, Database: Academic Search Premier, Vol. 93, (48).
7. Barbara Loecher, Sep 2004, Catch Your Breath and Save Your Life, Prevention,00328006, California Environmental Protection Agency and the US Surgeon General, Vol. 56 .
8. Bethesda, MD , 2004. National Cancer Institute. Health effects of exposure to environmental tobacco smoke: the report of the California Environmental Protection Agency.: US Department of Health and Human Services, National Institutes of Health, National Cancer Institute
9. David Lee et al, Jan/Feb2004, Secondhand smoke exposure and earaches in adolescents: The Florida Youth Cohort Study, Journal of Public Health Management & Practice, Vol. 10(1), p35.
10. Erik Velasco ,at al , Sep 2004, Exploratory Study of Particle-bound Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons in Different Environments of Mexico City, Atmospheric Environment, Vol. 38, (29), p495
11. Firsthand 8/9/2004, Evidence of Secondhand Smoke Effects, Pediatric Alert, 01600184, , Database: Academic Search Premier, Vol. 26, (15) Good Housekeeping, July 2003, Vol. 237, (1), p63.
12. Harder, B 1/15/2005, , Living in a Fog, Science News, 00368423, Vol. 167
13. Henderson, A.J. 2008. The effects of tobacco smoke exposure on respiratory health in school-aged children. Paediatric Respiratory Reviews Vol. 9, 21-28.Consulted: 22.11.2010
14. IARC 2004(exposure to secondhand or 'environmental' tobacco smoke Keith King at al, Sep/Oct. 2003, Smokers' willingness to protect Children from secondhand smoke, American Journal of Health Behavior, Vol. 27, (5), p554
15. Patrick Perry at al, Jul/Aug2002, Tobacco: making a Killing, Saturday Evening Post, 00489239, , Database: Academic Search Premier, Vol. 274, (4)
16. Peachick TF et al Commentary 8/30.2004, How acute and reversible are the cardiovascular risks of secondhand smoke, Vol.164, (9).
17. Sanjay Gupta, 2003,Asthma-Proofing Your Home, Secondhand Smoke Linked to Tooth Decay, Journal of Dental Hygiene, Spring Secondhand Smoke Exposure Among Middle and High School Students, Vol. 77, (2), p78 • Secondhand Smoke.